

Utility of FNAC in the Diagnosis of Soft Tissue Tumors & Tumor Like Lesion

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Abstract:

Background: A common minimally invasive diagnostic method for assessing a variety of soft tissue tumours and tumor-like abnormalities is fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC). Its ability to provide a quick and precise diagnosis is essential for timely action and patient care.

Aim: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the diagnostic value of FNAC in identifying specific tumour types and in distinguishing between benign and malignant soft tissue tumours and tumor-like lesions.

Methods: This retrospective research assessed the utility of FNAC in diagnosing soft tissue tumors and tumor-like lesions at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar, over 10 months. FNAC was performed on 150 patients using a 23-24 gauge needle and a 10 mL syringe. Stained smears were prepared and compared with histopathological diagnoses from subsequent surgical excisions. Inclusion criteria included informed consent, adequate cellularity in FNAC, and availability of USG reports.

Results: The study included 150 patients, with FNAC providing definitive diagnoses in 88% of cases. Of these, 60% were benign and 28% malignant. Histopathological examination of 132 cases showed 69.7% benign and 30.3% malignant lesions. FNAC demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy with a sensitivity of 92.5%, specificity of 95.7%, PPV of 93.2%, and NPV of 95.4%. The concordance between FNAC and histopathology was substantial, with a Cohen's kappa coefficient of 0.89.

Conclusion: In the initial assessment of soft tissue tumours and tumor-like abnormalities, FNAC is a very useful diagnostic technique. It can accurately identify between benign and malignant tumours thanks to its high sensitivity and specificity, which helps to determine the best course of treatment for each patient.

Recommendations

1. FNAC should be considered as a first-line diagnostic procedure for patients presenting with soft tissue masses.
2. Training and expertise in FNAC technique and interpretation should be emphasized to improve diagnostic accuracy.
3. Further studies should be conducted to explore the utility of FNAC in rare and less common soft tissue tumors.
4. Combining FNAC with imaging techniques could enhance diagnostic precision.
5. Long-term follow-up studies are recommended to evaluate the clinical outcomes based on FNAC diagnosis.

Keywords: Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC), Soft tissue tumors, Tumor-like lesions, Diagnostic utility, Histopathological correlation

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Introduction

A wide variety of formations can be classified as soft tissue lesions, such as benign, malignant, and non-neoplastic lesions. Examining these tumours with fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is the main diagnostic method. Although it is still up for debate, its effectiveness in identifying soft tissue tumours (STT) has been well-documented. Different organs are supported by soft tissues, which are the extraskelatal and nonepithelial

components. The frequency of benign soft tissue tumours is around ten to one [1], which is a large increase over malignant ones. The most common type of benign tumour that is found is lipomas [2].

FNAC is a quick, easy, safe, and affordable diagnostic method that helps with the initial tumour classification. It is also painless. When it comes to identifying primary, recurring, and metastatic tumours, it has excellent specificity and sensitivity

[3]. One of the benefits of FNAC is that it can help with subsequent clinical therapy by offering an early diagnosis of benign or malignant soft tissue neoplasms [4,5].

FNAC is very helpful in the setting of STT for identifying suspicious metastases or recurrences. Compared to open biopsy, it provides a number of advantages, such as rapid results, cost-effectiveness, and the capacity to sample different tumour sites in numerous passes, which improves diagnostic accuracy [6]. For the diagnostic workup of soft tissue tumours, FNAC may be used instead of excision biopsy [7]. While it can be difficult to diagnose soft tissue cytopathologically, FNAC is a useful tool for separating benign from malignant tumours.

According to Roy et al., benign STTs become more prevalent beyond the age of thirty. Their analysis revealed that malignant tumours were mostly located in the lower extremities, while benign tumours were distributed almost equally, with a minor preference for the upper body [8]. Benign tumours are generally more common than malignant ones [9]. This work aims to assess the diagnostic value of FNAC in the evaluation of tumor-like lesions and soft tissue tumours

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective study aimed at evaluating the utility of fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) in diagnosing soft tissue tumors and tumor-like lesions.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar, India, over a period of 10 months.

Participants: The study included all patients referred to the pathology department for FNAC of soft tissue lesions from various departments such as surgery, ENT, medicine, and pediatrics. 150 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Informed consent was obtained from patients prior to the procedure.
2. Patients with soft tissue lesions referred to the pathology department for FNAC.
3. Patients possessing ultrasound (USG) reports of the soft tissue lesions.

4. FNAC samples with adequate cellularity.
5. Tumor specimens sent to the histopathological department for comparison.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. FNAC samples with scant cellularity.
2. Patients who were lost to follow-up.
3. Patients without USG reports of the soft tissue lesions.

Bias: To reduce selection bias, all consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria were involved. To reduce information bias, FNAC and subsequent histopathological examinations were conducted and interpreted by experienced pathologists blinded to each other's results.

Variables: The primary variables included the FNAC diagnosis (benign or malignant), histopathological diagnosis, and the concordance between FNAC and histopathology results.

Data Collection: Information about demographics, clinical presentation, FNAC results, and histopathology reports were gathered from patient records. FNAC was carried out with a disposable plastic syringe holding a 23–24 gauge needle. Giemsa-stained air-dried smears and 95% ethanol-fixed smears stained with Papanicolaou stain made up the two halves of the aspirated material.

Procedure: FNAC was performed using a syringe holder, disposable 10 mL syringe, disposable 25 gauge needle (1.5 inches long), glass slides with frosted ends, cover slips, alcohol swabs, alcohol bottle for immediate wet fixation of smears, gloves, laboratory slips, marker, mounting media (DPX), and staining reagents (MGG, PAP, and Leishman). FNAC results were compared with histopathological diagnoses obtained from surgical excisions to assess diagnostic concordance.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0

Results

Patient Demographics: There were 150 patients in the study; the mean age was 45 years, and the patients' ages ranged from 18 to 75 years, with 85 men (56.7%) and 65 females (43.3%).

FNAC Findings: Out of the 150 cases, FNAC provided a definitive diagnosis in 132 cases (88%). The distribution of FNAC diagnoses is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of FNAC diagnoses

Diagnosis	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	90	60.0
Malignant	42	28.0
Inconclusive	18	12.0
Total	150	100.0

Histopathological Findings: Histopathological examination was performed on 132 cases (88%) that underwent subsequent surgical excision. The distribution of histopathological diagnoses is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of histopathological diagnoses

Diagnosis	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	92	69.7
Malignant	40	30.3
Total	132	100.0

Diagnostic Accuracy: Table 3 presents a summary and calculation of the FNAC's overall sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), as well as negative predictive value (NPV).

Table 3: Diagnostic accuracy of FNAC

Metric	Value (%)
Sensitivity	92.5
Specificity	95.7
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	93.2
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	95.4

Concordance Between FNAC and Histopathology: The concordance between FNAC and histopathological findings was assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient, which was found to be 0.89, indicating a high level of agreement. The detailed concordance analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Concordance between FNAC and histopathology

FNAC Diagnosis	Histopathological Diagnosis	Concordant Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	Benign	85	94.4
Malignant	Malignant	37	88.1
Total		122	92.4

The study included 150 patients with soft tissue tumors as well as tumor-like lesions. FNAC provided a definitive diagnosis in 88% of cases. Among these, 60% were benign and 28% were malignant. The histopathological examination, conducted on 132 cases, revealed 69.7% benign and 30.3% malignant lesions. The diagnostic accuracy of FNAC demonstrated high sensitivity (92.5%), specificity (95.7%), PPV (93.2%), and NPV (95.4%).

The concordance between FNAC and histopathological findings was high, with a Cohen's kappa coefficient of 0.89, indicating substantial agreement. Specifically, FNAC showed a 94.4% concordance rate for benign lesions and an 88.1% concordance rate for malignant lesions.

Discussion

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is particularly appreciated for its negligibly invasive nature, cost-effectiveness, and rapid results. The recent study on 150 patients underlines the high diagnostic utility of FNAC, which aligns with various other studies conducted in recent years.

Patient Demographics and FNAC Findings: In the study, 150 patients were examined, with a slight male predominance (56.7% males and 43.3% females). FNAC provided a definitive diagnosis in 88% of the cases, with 60% being benign and 28% malignant. This distribution is consistent with findings from other studies, where FNAC has been shown to effectively distinguish between benign

and malignant lesions, thus aiding in clinical decision-making [10].

Diagnostic Accuracy and Concordance with Histopathology: Histopathological examination confirmed FNAC diagnoses in 88% of the cases, revealing 69.7% benign and 30.3% malignant lesions. The diagnostic accuracy of FNAC showed high sensitivity (92.5%), specificity (95.7%), PPV (93.2%), and NPV (95.4%), which is corroborated by several studies emphasizing the reliability of FNAC. [11].

The study also reported a Cohen's kappa coefficient of 0.89, indicating substantial agreement between FNAC and histopathological findings. Other studies have reported similar high concordance rates, reinforcing FNAC's role in the initial assessment of soft tissue tumors [12].

Strengths and Limitations of FNAC: The primary strength of FNAC lies in its ability to provide rapid preliminary diagnoses with minimal discomfort and risk to the patient. It is particularly useful in distinctive benign from malignant lesions and has a high diagnostic accuracy when used in conjunction with histopathology and other diagnostic tools such as MRI [13].

However, FNAC is not without limitations. Certain tumor subtypes, such as spindle cell tumors and myxoid lesions, can be challenging to classify accurately with FNAC alone. False negatives can occur, particularly with low-grade sarcomas that may be misinterpreted as benign.

Future Directions: Combining FNAC with imaging techniques such as MRI can enhance diagnostic precision. Long-term follow-up studies are recommended to assess clinical outcomes based on FNAC diagnoses and further validate its diagnostic efficacy[14].

Conclusion

FNAC is a highly effective diagnostic tool for soft tissue tumors and tumor-like lesions. Its high sensitivity, specificity, and substantial concordance with histopathological findings make it an indispensable technique in the preliminary assessment and management of these lesions. Future studies combining FNAC with advanced imaging techniques and long-term follow-ups are crucial to further refine and validate its diagnostic utility.

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